

D5.1 Guide for preparation administration and management of European project for UPJS staff

Name of project: **Fostering high scientific quality in protein research in Eastern
Slovakia (CasProt)**

No. 952333

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Leader/Coordinator of the project CasProt – Pavol Jozef Šafárik University in Košice (UPJŠ) formulated the following Guide for preparation administration and management of European project for UPJŠ staff divided to several chapters such as introduction/purpose of the guideline, principles of the preparation and submission of the project application and principles of the project implementation.

Without good research content, the administration is not able to strengthen the help, so the motivation should come especially from researchers - Having a great content is essential. Projects must fit into broader strategies, so overall university cooperation and good processes are necessary for improving project funding finding. The university should provide multilateral support to young researchers and create good conditions to develop their skills and transform their ideas into business ideas that should bring overall social benefits. Inspired by partner universities' departments, people from UPJŠ project support will do their best to provide focused, professional and personalized assistance.

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1. Introduction / Purpose and content of the Guideline

European projects are collaborative initiatives funded by the European Union (EU) that aim to address societal challenges and foster innovation and cooperation across Europe. These projects involve multiple partners from different countries and require effective preparation, administration, and management to ensure their success. In this guide, we will provide an overview of the key steps involved in preparing, administering, and managing a European project.

UPJŠ involvement in international research consortia through horizontal EU programs has its specificities, which are different from Slovak national funding schemes for science and research. Given that information about UPJŠ is published in the Funding & tenders' opportunities portal (F&T portal), UPJŠ's uniform approach to published information during the life cycle of Horizon Europe (HEU) projects is necessary.

More specifically, this guideline is designed to help you to maximise the potential for your projects to succeed by helping you address each element of your project at the right time and to the right level of detail for the size and complexity of your project.

When preparing project plans, it is essential to follow these documents:

- AMGA - Annotated Model Grant Agreement
- Strategy of human resources in research at UPJŠ (HRS4R)
- Gender equality plan at the UPJŠ for the period 2022-2025
- Act no. 18/2018 Coll. on the protection of personal data and on the amendment of certain laws ("Act No. 18/2018 Coll. of")
- Update of the Long-Term Plan of the UPJŠ for the years 2020 to 2025
- CODE OF ETHICS of the UPJŠ
- Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council (EU) on the protection of natural persons during processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, which repeals Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), known as GDPR
- Other EC documents related to OPEN SCIENCE & OPEN DATA

1.1 Horizon Europe program

Horizon Europe (HEU) - 9th EU framework program for research and innovation. The HEU program in the period of years 2021 to 2027 seamlessly follows on from the Horizon 2020 program. The budget of the HEU program has stabilized at 84.9 billion EUR in 2018 prices, which amounts to 95.5 billion EUR at current prices. The HEU is implemented through work programs that set out options funding mainly through calls for proposals.

Figure 1. Structure of Horizon Europe program

1.2 Basic terms in HEU

Audit - official control carried out by independent auditors in the premises of the beneficiaries with the aim check compliance with the conditions in the grant agreement; it can be a financial audit (checking of accounts and records of beneficiaries) or about performance audit (verification of project implementation and results); It ends with a report issued after the objection procedure.

Associated country - a country outside the EU that has concluded a special agreement ("agreement on association") with the EU on participation in a specific EU funding fund/programme.

Affiliated entity - have a legal and/or capital connection to the recipient (e.g., parent company, subsidiary, associated companies). They perform tasks within the project, and they declare their own costs (the non-profit rule applies!) in the project.

Annotated Model Grant Agreement – AMGA - contains interpretations of GA provisions and a set of practical one's examples to resolve doubts that may arise when applying the rules in practice.

Associated Partner - is usually an entity (company, university, etc.) from a non-member state of the European Union and which receives funding from its own national authority financing.

Beneficiary - partner/recipient - person or organization that receives EU funds in the form of a grant.

Call - the procedure of inviting applicants to submit project proposals with the aim of obtaining funding EU funds, divided by topic.

There are several types of challenges (with special submission or rating schemes):

- 2-stage calls - two-round calls.
- 1-stage calls - one-round calls.
- calls with multiple cut-off dates – calls with multiple cut-off dates.

Consortium - a group of recipients or procurers.

Consortium agreement – CA - internal agreement between consortium members; establishes their rights and obligations in implementing the project in accordance with the grant agreement.

Certificate of financial statement - a report prepared by an independent auditor, the purpose of which is enable the European Commission or the grant agency to check whether the costs declared in financial statements authorized.

Cordis - EC IT tool for storing and publishing general data on all research EU-funded projects and their results (H2020, FP7 and previous framework programs for research).

Coordination and support actions - CSA - type of project consisting mainly of accompanying measures or complementary activities, such as: standardization, dissemination, awareness raising and communication, networking, coordination or support services, political dialogue, exercises mutual learning, study, networking and coordination between programs in different countries.

Deliverable - The specific output of the project in terms of the overall goals of the project in the form of a report, document, technical diagram, software, etc.

Dissemination - the process of publishing project results.

European Research Council - ERC - EU body established for support researcher-led research at the frontiers of knowledge; its purpose is to stimulate scientific excellence and encourage scientists, academics and engineers in their research.

European Commission - EC - grant provider from the Framework Programme.

Exploitation - means for using the results created within the EU project in other activities (other than those covered by the project, e.g. in other research activities; development, creation and marketing of a product, process or service; during normalization activities).

Financial report - states the consumption of project costs spent during of the given reporting period. Together with the Technical report, it forms a report for the data reporting period/Periodic report.

Flat rate - indicates the price structure charged by one fixed for the service fee regardless of its use.

Financial Support for Third Parties - FSTP - financial support for third parties.

Grant Agreement - GA.

Innovation action - IA - a type of project aimed at creating plans and arrangements or proposals new, changed or improved products, processes or services including prototyping, testing, demonstration, piloting, large-scale product validation, market replication, TRL 4-8, there must be an SME in the consortium, the project must result from an increase in TRL.

Internally invoiced goods and services - IIGS - costs of goods and services that are produced, or they provide within the recipient's organization directly in connection with the implementation of the project intent based on its normal cost accounting practices.

Institutional Costs - are expenses universities spent on support and research support, which cannot be precisely itemized costs attributable to an individual research project.

Interim payments - cover authorized costs incurred during project implementation during the corresponding reporting periods.

Lump sum - a one-time payment made at a certain time as opposed to several smaller payments; in the case of lump sum grants, the financial audit is not only technical.

Milestones - checkpoints in the project that help map progress; can answer the completion of a key output, which will allow the next phase of work to begin; however, they may also be needed in transitional phases so that corrective measures can be taken in case of any that arise problems.

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions - MSCA - project scheme aimed at supporting international, interdisciplinary and intersectoral mobility. The help is aimed at all scientific fields (bottom-up approach). Its aim is to support human resources, mobility, further education and professional growth researchers at European or international level. They can participate in MSC events novice as well as experienced researchers. The basic condition for participation in MSCA is international mobility, i.e., researchers have to move from one country to another in order to deepen their professional knowledge and competences.

Review meeting - evaluation meeting - organized by the EC project manager with an external expert and project participants for the purpose of evaluating the work plan, outputs and milestones of the project.

Small or Medium Enterprise - SME – (in Slovak MSP) – as defined in EU Recommendation 2003/361; In order to the company has qualified for EU funding as an SME, it must meet certain conditions including: less than 250 employees, an annual turnover of no more than EUR 50 million and/or a total annual balance sheet a maximum of EUR 43 million.

Pre-financing payment - an advance payment that will enable you to finance the costs of project.

Project coordinator - is the leader of the consortium.

Project manager - is the partner's project manager.

Project manager EC - project officer from the EU - assigned manager on the EU side.

Project proposal - project application - request for funding from the EU, submitted in response to a call.

Participant Identification Code/PIC Number - unique registration number in the F&T portal. PIC Number UPJŠ: 999885992.

Payment of the balance - the amount to be paid (or recovered) when paying the balance (final payment). It is calculated by the EC/agency on the basis of financial statements, the final amount of the grant and already made payments. If the final amount of the grant is higher than the payments already made, the balance will take the form of payment; if the final amount of the grant is less than the payments made, the balance will have a return form.

Person-month - is a metric of time (effort) devoted by key personnel of the organization a specific project.

Report - regular assessment of project progress and incurred costs (and submission EU reports); usually associated with reporting periods and interim payments.

Reporting period - longer projects are divided into reporting periods in order regular reporting and interim payments were made possible.

Research & innovation actions – RIA - type of project focused on acquiring new knowledge and/or investigating the feasibility of a new or improved technology, product, process, service or solutions that include: basic and applied research, development and integration of technologies, testing and validation on a small prototype in a laboratory or simulated environment, closely related but limited demonstration or pilot activities aimed at demonstrating technical feasibility in an environment close to operation, TRL 1-7, the project must result from an increase in TRL, grant in the amount of 100%.

Subcontract - **SC** - an agreement between the recipient and the subcontractor who performs the project tasks for the beneficiary without direct supervision and without a subordinate relationship; it is also used in procurement with essentially the same meaning.

Technical report - describes the procedure, achieved results of scientific and technical work on the project. Together with the Financial report/Technical report, it forms the report for the given reporting period/ Periodic report.

Task - activity within the work package.

Third party - an entity that is involved in the project without becoming a financial recipient funds, e.g., by providing non-monetary contributions or services to the recipient for payment.

Timesheet - work report - reports of work spent on the project.

Topic - calls for proposals are divided into topics; a topic defines a specific subject or the area for which applicants are invited to submit proposals; the description of the topic includes its specific scope, type of action, evaluation criteria and deadline for submission of proposals; 'call' and 'topic' often are used as synonyms.

Technology readiness level – TRL - is a method for defining the maturity of a product and its relation to the market. The European Commission decided to introduce it in its research and innovation projects since Horizon 2020 (H2020).

- TRL 1: basic principles observed;
- TRL 2: technology concept formulated;
- TRL 3: experimental proof of concept;
- TRL 4: technology validated in lab;
- TRL 5: technology validated in the relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key supporting technologies);
- TRL 6: technology proven in the relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key supporting technologies);
- TRL 7: system prototype demonstration in operational environment;
- TRL 8: system complete and qualified;

- TRL 9: actual system proven in operational environment (competitive production in case key supporting technologies or in space).

Unit cost - a total expenditure incurred by a company to produce, store, and sell one unit of a particular product or service.

Work Package - WP - (activity) work package containing each other related and precisely defined activities/tasks - Tasks.

Work program - EU programming and planning document; in area funding funds/programs, this means a (several) annual document by which the EC determines activities, which will be implemented during the duration of the program (i.e., grants, procurements, list of calls, etc.).

2. Principles for the preparation and submission of project applications

Figure 2. EU project cycle management

Step 1: Identify the Funding Opportunities and read the call documents

The first step in preparing a European project is **to identify the funding opportunities available**. This can be done by searching online on F&T Portal, for the current funding programs offered by the EU, or by contacting the relevant EU agencies or national contact points for specific programs. Once you have identified a suitable program, you will need to read the guidelines and expected outcomes carefully and ensure that your project fits the scope of the program.

Before starting to draft the proposal, **read the call documents carefully**. These include the Work Program, the Guide for Applicants, and the specific Call conditions. Pay attention to the eligibility criteria, the evaluation criteria, and the submission deadline.

Step 2: Form a Consortium

The next step is to **form a consortium of partners from different countries** who will participate in the project. The consortium should include partners with the necessary expertise and resources to carry out the project objectives. To form a consortium, you can use various online platforms or attend networking events (brokerage events, webinars, etc.) to meet potential partners. Once you have identified potential partners, reach out to them and discuss your proposal idea and define the roles and responsibilities of each partner in the consortium based on their expertise and contribution towards the project.

Step 3: Define the Project Objectives and Work Plan

Once you have formed a consortium, you will need **to define the project objectives and work plan**. This involves identifying the project's research questions, setting out the project milestones and deliverables, and defining the roles and responsibilities of each partner. It is important to involve all partners in this process to ensure a shared understanding of the project's goals and objectives.

Step 4: Write the Proposal

The next step is **to write the project proposal**, which will be submitted to the relevant EU agency for funding consideration. The proposal should be clear, concise, and include all the necessary **information about the project objectives, methodology, expected outcomes, and impact**. It is essential to ensure that the proposal is written in accordance with the guidelines provided by the EU agency.

The following are some key steps involved in project preparation:

- 1. Define the evaluation criteria:** Identify the key performance indicators (KPIs) that will be used to measure the success of the project. These may include financial metrics, such as return on investment (ROI), schedule and timeline adherence, quality of deliverables, stakeholder satisfaction, and others.
- 2. Collect data:** Gather information from various sources, such as project documents, surveys, meetings, interviews, and feedback from stakeholders. Make sure the data is accurate, reliable, and relevant to the evaluation criteria.
- 3. Analyse the data:** Use analytical tools and techniques to assess the data and draw conclusions about the project's performance. Identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT analysis) and develop recommendations for improvement.

Step 5: Budget preparation

Once the proposal has been prepared, you will need **to form a detailed budget for the project**. This should include all the costs associated with carrying out the project, such as personnel costs, travel expenses, equipment costs, and overheads. The budget should be realistic and in line with the funding available and it is created based on the estimate of authorized costs of individual partners consortium (and associated entities).

The personnel cost of the project is the price of the employee's work, including the employee's contributions and the employer and other payments resulting from valid legislation and internal regulations UPJŠ.

The maximum amount of EC contribution (approved in the GA) cannot be during the implementation of the project increased.

What to pay attention to when planning:

- respect the normal accounting practice in the organization;
- financial rules of the HEU program;
- third parties in the project (subcontracts); about predicting inflation and wage growth.

A. Personnel costs	B. Subcontracts	C. Purchase costs	D. Other costs categories	E. Indirect costs
A.1 Employees A.2 Natural persons with direct contract A.3 Seconded employees and the seconded contractors A.4 SME owners and natural person		C.1 Travel and subsistence C.2 Equipment C.3 Other goods, works and services	D.1 Financial support to third parties D.2 Internally invoiced goods and services D.3 Transnational access to Research Infrastructures D.4 Virtual Access to Research Infrastructures D.5 PCP/PPI Procurement costs D.6 Euratom Cofund staff mobility costs D.7 ERC additional funding D.8 ERC additional funding - SC, FSTP, IIGS	

Figure 3. Standard structure of budget in HEU program

A Personnel costs

Personnel costs for employees include salaries and other benefits of workers and other employees of the research team.

A.1 Employees

An employee of UPJŠ for the purposes of project records is a person with a valid employment contract with UPJŠ during the implementation of project activities, which meets the following conditions:

- is an employee of UPJŠ in one of the following employment-legal relationships according to the definition of the Labor Code:
 - employment relationship (functional salary or personal salary);
 - reduced employment (functional salary or personal salary);
- remuneration of the employee is in accordance with the normal practice of UPJŠ;
- this budget category covers the cost of employees or the equivalent who worked within the action, i.e., persons working for the beneficiary under an employment contract or equivalent appointment act;
- costs for employees must be declared as actual personnel costs.

Authorized personnel costs for calculating daily rate:

- fixed wage/salary;
- fixed remuneration components, valid for all those entitled to payment, e.g., by law or collective agreement;
- variable wage components
 - based on objective criteria and defined at least in an internal directive;
 - paid consistently;
- mandatory employee and employer contributions to the social and health insurance company; about income tax;
- other costs and payments associated with remuneration, if they are authorized and registered as personal expenses in accordance with the recipient's usual remuneration procedures.

Unauthorized personnel costs for calculating daily rate:

- for any part of the reward that was not an actual cost to you;
- dividend payments to employees;
- any part of the reward that is based on business objectives or fundraising; about arbitrary bonuses (arbitrary bonuses), i.e., bonuses that are not paid based objective conditions set at least in internal guidelines recipient or bonuses that are paid inconsistently;
- bonuses that depend on the availability of the budget for a specific project.

Calculation of personnel costs for employees

Types of calculation of personnel costs for employees:

- corporate approach - remuneration does not change due to participation in projects;
- project remuneration - as a result of participation in projects, remuneration changes.

When calculating personnel costs for employees, the corporate approach is applied within UPJŠ.

Calculation procedure

The calculation of authorized personnel costs consists of two basic equations. Daily calculation rates using 215 working days and multiplying it by the number of days spent on the project.

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{Personnel costs} = \text{daily rate} \times \text{number of days worked on the project} \\ \text{Daily rate} = \frac{\text{actual annual personnel costs}}{215} \end{array}$$

Figure 4. Calculation of personnel costs and daily rate in HEU

1.) On the basis of the recapitulation of salaries and contributions, it is necessary to calculate **the actual annual personnel costs** to the given project manager for the entire calendar year during which the employee worked on the project.

- If the researcher has worked at UPJŠ for a whole year - a recalculation will be carried out at the level of the whole year.
- If the researcher was employed at UPJŠ only for a certain part of the year, e.g., 3 months, it is necessary to calculate his personnel costs only for the given 3 months.
- It is rounded to the nearest half-day.
- Under the conditions of UPJŠ, one working day is 7.5 hours.

Actual annual personnel costs = fixed salary (tariff salary, supplement, allowances) + mandatory contributions.

Unauthorized wage components: Remuneration, employer's contribution to supplementary pension savings, contributions from the social fund, etc. and the associated levies.

2.) Based on the amount of working time and the number of months worked, it is necessary to calculate **the number productive days** belonging to the given solver.

215 = fixed number of productive days (maximum possible value for one calendar year)

Example of calculation for a change in working hours during the reporting period:

In the reporting period from 01/01/2022 to 31/03/2023, the employee worked full-time in 2022 (12 months) and for 50% full-time in 2023 (3 months):

12 months = full time: $((215 / 12) \times 12) \times 1 = 215$

3 months = part-time: $((215 / 12) \times 3) \times 0.5 = 27$

Number of productive days: 215 + 27 = 242 (maximum possible value for this case)

$$\text{Daily rate} = \text{actual annual personnel costs} / \text{number of productive days}$$

List of usual documents:

- calculation/determination of productive days per calendar year (for determining the value of person month for the project);
- determining the daily rate for each member of the project team;
- the employment contract of each member of the project team, including all amendments, which is controlled on the basis of substantive, legal and financial compliance;
- working time record methodology (attendance book or electronic attendance);
- timesheet is a document that records work-related performance with the employee's time together with the monthly work report signed by the employee and management staff; which is controlled on a factual, legal and financial basis compliance (confirmation by signature from a senior employee/project manager or coordinator or dean/rector or secretary/quaestor);
- wage regulation;
- pay slip;
- accounting document on the payment of wages, levies and taxes;
- statement from the salary account on the payment of salaries, levies, taxes.

Working time recording methodology:

1. The monthly/annual working time is used to record the working time of individual employees the report (Timesheet), the sample of which was provided by the EC. You can use your own form for each project or a form provided by an EU project officer or adapted by agreement in the consortium and contains at least the following data:

- name of the organization;
- name and surname of the employee;
- designation of the period covered by the report (month and year);
- differentiation of individual work activities within working hours;
- registration of hours for individual activities - in total up to the amount of full-time work;
- description of the employee's employment relationship, or working hours in the case of a worker contracts;
- signature of the employee;
- graphic marking according to EU rules;
- signature of the authorized senior employee.

2. The record of working time makes it possible to distinguish working time between individual EC-financed projects in the event that an employee performs the activities of several projects (or roles) within the scope of the employment contract.

3. If an employee works on several projects, it is necessary to use the UPJŠ internal portal (Project Management IS) to edit working hours on EC-funded projects.

A.2 Natural persons with direct contract

Costs of natural persons working on the basis of a direct contract (e.g. Employment Agreement performed outside the employment relationship).

A.3 Personnel sent by a third party for remuneration/ Seconded persons (Seconded Employees and the Seconded Contractors)

Personnel on the basis of an agreement on the temporary assignment of an employee (between employers, also between employer and employee).

A.4 Owners of SMEs and FOs who do not pay their wages / SME owners and natural persons

Costs must be calculated for the SME owner/natural person in accordance with the methodology established EK.

B Subcontracts

- An entity that does not sign the GA, but directly participates in comprehensive project tasks and a subcontract must be planned in advance (or approved ex post in a periodic report). He usually carries out the implementation of a specific contract according to GA/the entire Task.
- The contract between the subcontractor and the recipient is based on the business conditions in accordance with applicable legislation and the Public Procurement Act.
- Subcontracting costs are not included in the basis for calculating indirect costs (for difference from supplier costs – other direct costs).
- Subcontracting between partners is not allowed.
- They must be in accordance with the recipient's normal practice; meet the criterion of the best quality/price ratio and are not in conflict of interest.
- The subcontractor is responsible to the recipient (not EC).
- The range of subcontracts is generally limited.
- The coordinator's activities related to the management of the consortium cannot be performed by a subcontractor.

List of usual documents:

- subcontracting schedule (including purpose and timing);
- public procurement documents according to the valid Act on Public Procurement;
- public procurement announcement;

- market research for orders according to the Act on Vocational Training and internal guidelines;
- evaluation of public procurement - together with material control; legal and budget compliance;
- contract or order;
- invoice liquidation letter - which includes confirmation of order receipt, material, legal and budgetary compliance check, invoice, delivery note, protocols and others;
- proof of payment;
- record of service delivery.

C Purchase costs

- they must be in accordance with the normal practice of the recipient, meet the criteria of the best quality/price ratio and not to be in a conflict of interest;
- in some cases, the EC may set additional conditions for the procurement process (specified in the call): e.g., min. number of offers, publication in the Official Journal, on the Internet, newspapers;
- if they exceed 15% of personnel costs, they must be described in Part B (tab. 3.1h) in the application for a grant/Proposal.

C.1 Travel and subsistence

- travel reimbursements are administered in accordance with the applicable legislation, namely Act no. 283/2002 Coll. - Act on Travel Reimbursements and valid directive no. 3/2007 on provision travel allowances for employees of UPJŠ in Košice, no. j. 3150/2007 of 19.9.2007, as amended applicable amendments;
- the eligibility of travel reimbursements must be in accordance with the project intention;
- further arrangements regarding the drawing of flat rates are within the competence of the management of a specific project, as several schemes can be used to reimburse travel expenses compensation according to the characteristics of a specific project.

List of usual documents:

- travel order with consent for a business trip (signed by the relevant persons based on directive on the circulation of travel documents), submitted on the basis of justification and evidence invitations, containing (if relevant) a completed agreement on the use of a private motor vehicle together with a copy of the motor vehicle's documents and a copy of its insurance, information on the financing of the business trip (name of the project), specification of the work task/WP & Task;
- provision of accommodation and flight tickets is governed by the rules of the VO at the university. In case if in time of immediate PC preparation, no Framework Agreement for the provision of services is valid associated with securing plane tickets and accommodation

for the needs of UPJŠ in Košice, the employee submits a market survey (3 offers) justifying the economy of the given purchase;

- travel documents (as an attachment) - in case of application:
 - about actual travel costs: confirmation of payment from the accommodation facility (hotel), air ticket (boarding tickets), travel ticket, use of private car, taxi bill, other documents;
 - flat-rate travel expenses: plane ticket, travel ticket, use of private of a motor vehicle reimbursed in the amount of public transport;
- business trip report defining project name, WP and Task, with cost accounting of business trips, which contain information about the business trip, accounting for expenses for work trip according to the IS SOFIA system form, physical, legal and financial control the compliance on the basis of which the order for payment of costs is given;
- event program, invitations to stay, event attendance list and registration - if relevant;
- proof of payment of costs by the passenger.

C.2 Fixed assets/ Equipment/ Equipment

- Long-term assets (D tangible M - valuation higher than EUR 1700 with VAT and shelf life more than 1 year, D intangible M - valuation above 2400 EUR including VAT and shelf life more than 1 year);
- only in the form of accounting depreciation;
- only to the extent that corresponds to the use of the equipment on the project and the duration of the project;
- rental and leasing costs, if they do not exceed depreciation;
- in exceptional cases (if the call allows), they are eligible as fully capitalized costs (Full capitalized costs, Article 6.2.C.2 Equipment);
- the Beneficiary cannot claim depreciation for periods prior to the start of the project.

List of usual documents

- Public procurement plan – annual submission of requirements or operational request about additions to the VO plan;
- public procurement documents according to the valid Act on Public Procurement;
- public procurement announcement;
- market research for orders according to the Act on Vocational Training and internal guidelines;
- evaluation of public procurement - together with substantive, legal and budgetary control compliance;
- contract or order;

- invoice liquidation sheet - includes confirmation of receipt of the order, material, legal check and budget compliance, on the basis of which the invoice payment order is issued;
- proof of payment – account statement;
- property records;
- depreciation schedule;
- records on the use of property (journey book, records from devices, laboratory diaries, etc.).

C.3 Other goods, works and services/ Other goods, works and services

- Consumables and supplies (e.g., raw materials).
- Promotion and dissemination (e.g., fees for the conference at which they will be presented project results).
- Protection of intellectual property (e.g., fees to the patent office).
- Translations (if necessary).
- Publications (printing/flyer design).
- Certificates of financial statements and others.
- Audit expenses.
- Fees to ethics commissions.
- And others.

They are subject to public procurement.

D Other costs categories

D2 Goods delivered and services provided internally - internal organizational invoices

For all of them, we collect Internal invoices for goods and services/Internally invoiced goods and services – goods and services that occur during the administration of EC-financed projects in the practice of UPJŠ. These are goods or services provided within the recipient's organization directly for the project and valued by the recipient based on its normal cost accounting practices.

The costs of internally invoiced goods and services directly used for the project can be declared as unit costs according to the organization's usual cost accounting procedures, if they are declared eligible in the terms of the call, if they meet the general eligibility conditions for such unit costs. The amount per unit is calculated:

a) using the actual costs of goods or services recorded in the beneficiary's accounts, attributed either by direct measurement or on the basis of cost factors, and excluding any costs that are ineligible or already included in other budget categories; actual costs can be adjusted based on budgeted or estimated elements if they are relevant to the cost calculation, are reasonable and correspond to objective and verifiable information;

b) according to the usual cost accounting procedures, which are applied consistently, based on objective criteria, regardless of the source of funding

Even in the case of this type of costs, the recipient must observe/prove the principles of economy, efficiency, effectiveness and purposefulness. The recipient must justify the advantage of choosing internally supplied goods and services over externally supplied goods and services. D1, D3-D8 – these are specific types of costs, which this methodology does not discuss in detail (for more information see AGA).

E Indirect costs

- Costs that are related to project implementation only indirectly (service costs).
- A flat rate in the amount of 25% of eligible direct costs, excluding the costs of subcontracts, financial support for third parties and special categories of costs, if any, and internal invoices (indirect costs are already included in them in their actual amount).

F Other forms of budget

Fixed monthly unit contributions

In individual project scheme, the budget model is specified in the call. In addition to the usual, e.g., for MSCA (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action) projects, it uses a budget that is structured according to a fixed monthly unit allowance for the accepted researcher and a fixed monthly allowance for the institutional unit. Each of these two budget categories is divided into several categories, as shown in the illustrative table below.

	Contributions for the recruited researcher (per Person-month)					Institutional unit contributions (per person-month)	
	Living allowance	Mobility allowance	Family allowance (if applicable)	Long-term leave allowance (if applicable)	Special needs allowance (if applicable)	Research, training and networking contribution	Management and indirect contribution
MSCA DN	EUR 3,400 * country coefficient	EUR 600	EUR 660	EUR 4,000 x % covered by the beneficiary	requested unit x (1/number of months)	EUR 1,600	EUR 1,200
MSCA PF	EUR 5,080 * country coefficient	EUR 600	EUR 660	EUR 5 680 x % covered by the beneficiary	requested unit x (1/number of months)	EUR 1,000	EUR 650

Figure 5. Overview of unit costs

Lump sum projects

Projects where eligible costs are in the form of one-time contributions and are expenses directly related to project activities and WPs:

- Projects are no longer reimbursed on a cost reporting basis, but instead through a fixed lump sum payment.
- Lump sums have the potential to simplify the administrative burden (no reporting of costs, no need for work reports (Timesheets)).

Step 6: Submission of project application

The principles of submitting project proposals must be applied to all workplaces of the university. Submission of project applications within the horizontal programs HEU, LIFE, etc. is the *de jure* submission of project plans on behalf of UPJŠ. For this reason, it is necessary for employees to notify the Department of Lifelong Learning Centre and Projects Support (LLC&PS), which is responsible for the administration of the F&T portal at the central level of the university, about their interest in submitting a project or other requested action.

Before electronically participating in the project proposal, the applicant is obliged to:

- a) In the event that the applicant for UPJŠ appears in the project application as a member/partner in the form of joining an already generated project proposal, he is obliged to inform the LLC&PS framework program project support department about this fact at the e-mail address: horizon-office@upjs.sk and at the same time ask the leader of the consortium to grant "Access Rights" at the "Contact Person" level to horizon-office@upjs.sk in the F&T portal, in a specific request, in the "Participants List" section.
- b) In the event that the applicant for UPJŠ acts as a coordinator/leader of the consortium, he is obliged to inform the LLC&PS framework program project support department about this fact at the e-mail address: horizon-office@upjs.sk and at the same time set in the F&T portal, in a specific request, in the "Participants List" section, "Access Rights" at the "Contact person" level for horizon-office@upjs.sk.
- c) In the event that the applicant acts as a third party on behalf of UPJŠ, he is obliged to inform the support department of framework program projects from LLC&PS about this fact at the e-mail address: horizon-office@upjs.sk.
- d) If LLC&PS acts as a coordinator on behalf of an employee of any UPJŠ department/faculty during the preparation of a project application or participates as a partner in an already created project application, it informs the dean of the relevant faculty about the given fact with the aim of mutual information of all parties involved.

Step 7: Project Implementation and Management

Once the project has been approved and funded, it is time **to implement and manage the project**. This involves carrying out the project activities, monitoring progress against the work plan, managing the budget, and reporting on project outcomes. It is important to establish effective communication channels between partners and to hold regular project meetings to ensure that the project is on track.

Principles of administration during project implementation

1. After the announcement of the EC on the allocation of the grant, the employee responsible for the economic affairs of the faculty, in cooperation with the manager of LLC&PS, will request the Economic Department of the Rectorate to establish an interest-free account and to introduce budget allocations for the project.
2. After crediting funds from the EC to a special project bank account, the recipient has according to § 20 par. 8 of Act No. 523/2004 Coll. on the budgetary rules of public administration

and on amendments and additions to certain laws, the obligation to notify the Ministry of Finance of the Slovak Republic. Electronic notification must be submitted [HERE](https://www.mfsr.sk/sk/financne-vztahy-eu/oznamenie-prijati-financnej-pomoci-z-eu/elektronicke-podavanie-oznameni-prijati-pomoci-priamo-z-eu/elektronicke-oznamenie/) (https://www.mfsr.sk/sk/financne-vztahy-eu/oznamenie-prijati-financnej-pomoci-z-eu/elektronicke-podavanie-oznameni-prijati-pomoci-priamo-z-eu/elektronicke-oznamenie/).

3. We present the calculation of personnel costs and the Methodology for recording working hours in the Methodology section.
4. Changes to the budget that arise during implementation must, under certain conditions, be treated with a request for an amendment to the GA; all changes are recommended to be discussed in advance with the official assigned to the EC for the project (directly or through the consortium leader).
5. Accounting for indirect costs of the project:
 - In the event that the project scheme allows the application of indirect costs in the form of flat-rate reimbursements, UPJŠ will apply them on a monthly/quarterly basis or for a specific expenditure, namely the authorized amount according to the valid project budget or according to the agreement in the specific project as a proportional part calculated from the actual direct costs. The calculation is based on the actual costs calculated by the financial manager.
 - The application of flat-rate indirect costs is carried out by means of a payment order. A transfer request will be issued to the current account 637 021. The funds can subsequently be used to reimburse unspecified costs outside of unauthorized costs defined by the EU.
 - In case of payment of indirect expenses directly from the project bank account, the amount cannot exceed the amount of indirect costs for the given period.

Record of accounting documents and audit:

The HEU program involves a significant amount of funding for research and innovation projects that aim to address major societal challenges. Given the size and complexity of the programme, it is crucial to have robust accounting and audit procedures in place to ensure that funding is spent efficiently, effectively and in line with the programme's objectives.

A record of accounting documents is an essential component of the HEU program. This refers to a systematic means of documenting financial transactions relating to HEU projects, including receipts, invoices, contracts and other financial documents. The record should be comprehensive and kept up to date, ensuring that all financial transactions are accurately recorded and traceable.

In addition to maintaining a record of accounting documents, HEU projects are also subject to audit. An audit is an independent review of a project's financial records and activities, with the aim of verifying that the project has been conducted in accordance with the programme's rules and regulations. Audits are carried out by independent auditors and can be either internal or external.

The purpose of an audit in the HEU is to provide assurance that the programme's funds have been used in a responsible, efficient and effective manner. The audit will look at the project's financial records and transactions and assess whether they comply with the programme's rules and regulations.

It will also review the overall management of the project, including its governance structure and risk management processes.

The audit process is a critical component of the HEU program, as it helps to safeguard the programme's funding and ensure that it is being used to achieve its objectives. It also provides accountability and transparency, ensuring that stakeholders can have confidence in the programme's management and results. Overall, the record of accounting documents and audit processes are essential elements of the HEU program, helping to ensure its success in addressing some of the world's most pressing challenges through research and innovation.

The aim of document registration is to ensure the cooperation of UPJŠ in the event of a control audit (financial or technical) by the EU. The audit can take place during the implementation of the project or up to 5 years after the submission of the final project report.

For the stated reason, it is necessary **to archive the originals of all documents (signed by the relevant responsible persons) for at least 5 years** from the submission of the final project report. Archiving takes place in accordance with the registration rules of UPJŠ.

The threshold for CFS (Certificate on Financial Statement) audits in HEU is **EUR 430,000** (for each partner). If the EU contribution is higher, a CFS financial statement confirmation is required. In this case, it is necessary to carry out a public procurement for the contracting of an independent auditor, who will check accounting documents, accounting, internal regulations, internal processes, etc. and subsequently issues a certificate according to the methodology of the EC (link see sources).

Step 8: Project Evaluation and Reporting

At the end of the project, it is necessary **to evaluate the project's outcomes and report on the results**. This involves assessing the success of the project against the original objectives, identifying any lessons learned, and reporting on the impact of the project. It is essential to follow the reporting guidelines provided by the EU agency and to submit the report on time.

Project evaluation and reporting refer to the process of assessing and analysing the results and performance of a project and communicating the findings to relevant stakeholders. The purpose of project evaluation is to determine if the project has met its objectives, delivered its expected outcomes and benefits, stayed within its budget and timeline, and complied with applicable regulations and policies. Reporting involves presenting the evaluation findings in a clear and concise manner, using appropriate formats, tools, and channels.

Effective project evaluation and reporting are essential for ensuring the success of a project and maintaining transparency and accountability. By following a structured and systematic approach to evaluation and reporting, project managers can identify areas of improvement, make informed decisions, and enhance the overall value of the project.

Project evaluation and reporting are key components of the HEU program. To achieve these goals, project evaluation and reporting are critical to ensuring that the program is effective and efficient in achieving its objectives. These activities help to identify areas where improvements can be made, as well as highlight successes and best practices that can be shared with other projects. Project evaluation involves a rigorous, multi-stage process that starts with an initial screening

of proposed projects to determine their eligibility for funding. Once approved, projects undergo a more detailed evaluation that assesses their scientific, technical, and societal impact potential.

Evaluation criteria include the quality of the research proposal, the level of innovation, the feasibility of the project, and the potential to create economic and societal benefits. Proposals are evaluated by independent experts from across Europe who have relevant expertise in the specific areas covered by the project.

The following are some key steps involved in project reporting:

1. Prepare the technical report: Present the evaluation findings in a structured and logical format, using tables, charts, graphs, and other visual aids as appropriate. Include an executive summary, an overview of the evaluation process, the evaluation criteria and methods used, the results and analysis, and the recommendations.

2. Prepare the financial report:

- ***Familiarize yourself with the funding agreement:*** Before preparing the financial report, carefully read the funding agreement signed between your organization and the European Commission. This agreement outlines the financial reporting requirements specific to your project.
- ***Use the ECAS platform:*** To access the financial reporting system, you need to log in to the ECAS (European Commission Authentication System) platform. Here, you can submit and manage your financial reports.
- ***Gather financial data:*** Collect all financial documents related to your project, such as receipts, invoices, and bank statements. Ensure that these documents are properly organized and ready for submission.
- ***Fill in the forms:*** HEU financial reporting requires filling in three forms: Form C, Form D, and Form E. These forms detail the eligible costs incurred during the project, including personnel, equipment, and travel costs.
- ***Submit the financial reports:*** Once you have completed the forms, you need to submit them through the ECAS platform. The financial report should be submitted within 60 days after the end of the reporting period. If you miss this deadline, your organization may face a financial penalty. Financial report has to be sign by FSIGN, concretely for UPJŠ it is Ing. Silvia Medová.

In summary, preparing a financial report requires careful planning and attention to detail. By following the above steps, you can ensure that your financial report is accurate, complete, and submitted on time.

3. Communicate the report: Share the report with relevant stakeholders, including project sponsors, managers, team members, customers, and partners. Use appropriate communication channels, such as email, meetings, presentations, and reports.

4. Follow up: Monitor the implementation of the recommendations and report on the progress made. Conduct regular evaluations to track the project's performance over time and identify any changes that need to be made.

Reporting is also critical to the success of HEU projects. Recipients of funding are required to provide regular updates on the progress of their projects, including information on achievements, milestones, and any challenges that have been encountered. This information is used by program managers to monitor the effectiveness of projects and to identify opportunities for improvement.

In addition, reporting helps to ensure transparency and accountability in the use of public funds and helps to build trust and confidence in the program among stakeholders. Regular reporting also supports knowledge sharing and dissemination of best practices, which can help to increase the impact of HEU projects and promote innovation across Europe.

Sources

1. Annotated Model Grant Agreement Horizon Europe
https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf
2. Audit – online manual
<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/IT/Audits>
3. Funding and Tender Opportunities
<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home>
4. <https://enspire.science>
5. <https://innonews.blog/2017/09/22/tri-urovne-pripravenosti-technologie-ako-sa-definuju/>
6. <https://eraportal.sk/horizont-europa/>